

Chemistry of Isodithiobiurets. Part I. Oxidative Deallylation as an Alternative Route to the Synthesis of 3,5-Diarylimino-1,2,4-Dithiazolidines

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Some 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines have been synthesised by the oxidative deallylation of the corresponding 1,5-diarylimino-2-S allyliso-4-thiobiurets. Mechanism of the reaction has been discussed.

THE success of the oxidative debenzoylation technique in isodithiobiuret systems leading to the formation of substituted 1,2,4-dithiazolidines¹⁻⁴ has led us to study the oxidative deallylation reaction in 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets as an alternative route for the synthesis of 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines.

In the present communication the 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets (I) have been prepared by the condensation of the appropriate 1-aryl-2-S-allyliso-thiocarbamide with the required arylisothiocyanate. These isodithiobiurets (I) on oxidation with iodine in boiling chloroform afforded the corresponding 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (II). The structure of (II) was confirmed by their preparation by the direct oxidation of the related 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (III), which in turn were obtained by the reductive deallylation of the respective isodithiobiurets (I) with alkaline sulphide (vide Tables 1, 2 and 3) and also by the reduction of (II) to the corresponding 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets. The reaction can be represented as follows :

Mechanism : By analogy with the oxidative debenzoylation reaction mechanism⁴ the first step appears to proceed by the attack of the oxidant (iodine) on the sulphur atom of the >C=S group in position 4- of the isodithiobiurets (I). On account of the electromeric effect, the sulphur of the thio-carbonyl group tends to acquire a negative charge

(>C=S → >C⁺-S⁻) and thus offers a suitable site for attack by an electrophilic reagent such as the I⁺ available from the oxidant, forming a sulphenyl iodide salt (IV) as intermediate which eliminates allyl iodide and forms a dithiazolidine salt (V). Fig. 2.

Experimental

1,5-Diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets (I) : 1-Aryl-thiocarbamides were allylated with allylbromide⁵. The required aryl isothiocyanate and a benzene solution of the S-allylthiocarbamide base were mixed (1 : 1 mole) and heated on a water bath. The semisolid mass obtained on evaporation of the solvent,

where R and R' = phenyl-, p-tolyl-, p-Cl-phenyl- and p-anisyl group

Fig. 1.

on washing with petroleum ether and addition of a little ethanol, afforded the expected 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiuret as a crystalline product. It was recrystallised from ethanol. The results are summarized in Table 1.

3.5-Diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (II) :

(i) Oxidative deallylation of 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets with iodine in boiling chloroform : Iodine in boiling chloroform solution readily effected deallylation of 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets followed by ring closure to the related 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydroiodides.

afforded the free base, which was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 221°. These experimental results are recorded in Table 2.

(ii) Oxidation of 1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (III) with iodine in dilute ethanol : The 2,4-dithiobiurets listed in Table 3 were oxidised with iodine in ethanolic solution and ether added when the hydroiodides of the respective dithiazolidine precipitated. Free bases were obtained by treating these with ammonia. Dithiazolidine free bases were crystallised either from ethanol or chlorobenzene. These were found to be identical with the respective 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines recorded in Table 2, as no

Fig. 2.

For example, when to a solution of 1,5-di-*p*-Cl-phenyl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiuret (4 g) in boiling chloroform (15 ml) was added a hot solution of iodine (3 g) in chloroform (20 ml), the iodine was readily used up until in excess. On evaporation of the solvent and treatment of the residue with a small amount of ethanol, the expected dithiazolidine hydroiodide crystallised out. This on treatment with ammonia

depression in the mixed melting points were observed. The identity was further confirmed by superimposable I.R. spectra.

1,5-Diaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets :

(i) Reduction of (I) with hydrogen sulphide : The desired 1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiuret (Table 1) was dissolved in an ethanolic solution of sodium

TABLE I—1,5-DIARYL-2-S-ALLYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS

Reactants	1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets formed	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Found	Reqd.
S-allyl- <i>p</i> -anisyl-T + <i>p</i> -anisyl-I	1,5-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	65	99	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	C : 58.68 H : 5.28	58.91 5.42
S-allyl- <i>m</i> -tolyl-T + <i>m</i> -tolyl-I	1,5-di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	69	75	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂	C : 63.96 H : 5.83	64.22 5.91
S-allyl- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-T + <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-I	1,5-di- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	75	122	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	C : 50.64 H : 3.96	51.50 3.78
S-allyl- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-T + <i>m</i> -tolyl-I	1- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	70	84	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	C : 57.49 H : 4.56	57.52 4.79
S-allylphenyl-T + phenyl-I	1,5-diphenyl-	77	120	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	C : 63.52 H : 5.25	62.38 5.19
S-allyl phenyl-T + <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-I	1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	75	110	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S ₂	C : 55.99 H : 4.75	56.40 4.40
S-allyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + phenyl-I	1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-phenyl-	70	107	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂	C : 63.71 H : 5.16	63.34 5.57
S-allyl- <i>p</i> -tolyl-T + <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-I	1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	75	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ClN ₃ S ₂	C : 57.03 H : 5.13	57.52 4.79

T—denotes isothiocarbamide.

I—denotes isothiocyanate.

TABLE 2—3,5-DIARYLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES

2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiurets oxidised	3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine formed (free base)	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Found	Reqd.
1,5-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	3,5-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-imino-	50	175	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	C : 53.13 H : 4.43	53.65 4.34
1,5-di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	3,5-di- <i>m</i> -tolylimino-	60	153	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	C : 61.05 H : 4.74 N : 13.67	61.34 4.82 13.42
1,5-di- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	3,5-di- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-	63	221	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	C : 47.83 H : 3.61	47.40 3.50
1- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-3- <i>m</i> -tolylimino-	60	184	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	C : 54.34 H : 3.92	53.97 3.69
1,5-diphenyl-	3,5-diphenylimino-*	68	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	C : 58.21 H : 4.21	58.94 3.85
1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	5-phenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-	65	185	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	C : 52.19 H : 3.71	52.68 3.12
1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-phenyl-	5- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-3-phenylimino-	68	179	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	C : 60.03 H : 4.17	60.20 4.34
1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	5- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-	65	200	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	N : 16.10	15.59

*recorded⁶ m.p. 179°-80°.

TABLE 3—1,5-DIARYL-2,4-DITHIOBIURETS: REDUCTIVE DEALLYLATION OF 2-S-ALLYLISO-4-THIOBIURET (I) WITH HYDROGEN SULPHIDE

1,5-diaryl-2-S-allyliso-4-thiobiuret reduced	1,5-diaryl-2,4-dithiobiuret formed	M.P. °C	Formula	Found	Reqd.
1,5-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	1,5-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-	121	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	C : 55.55 H : 4.72	55.55 4.82
1,5-di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	1,5-di- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	124	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂	N : 13.03	13.33
1,5-di- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	1,5-di- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	163	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂	C : 47.86 H : 3.03	47.32 3.09
1- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	1- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-5- <i>m</i> -tolyl-	141	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	C : 52.98 H : 4.74	53.62 4.98
1,5-diphenyl-	1,5-diphenyl-*	143-44	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	N : 14.57	14.63
1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	1-phenyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	157	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	C : 53.19 H : 3.75	52.36 3.73
1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-phenyl-	1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-phenyl-	122	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	C : 59.09 H : 4.17	59.80 4.06
1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	1- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-	165	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ S ₂ Cl	N : 12.16	12.51

*recorded⁶ m.p. 144°.

sulphide (10%) and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 3-4 hrs. The resulting solution on filtration, neutralization with acetic acid and dilution with water, precipitated the dithiobiuret. These were crystallised from ethanol (Table 3).

(ii) Reduction of 1,2,4-dithiazolidines (II) with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide: The dithiazolidines were dissolved in hot, ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 30 min. The clear solution on dilution with water and acidification afforded the related 2,4-dithiobiuret (III). These were recrystallised from ethanol. No depression in melting point was observed when mixed with the respective 2,4-dithiobiurets recorded in Table 3. Their identities were further confirmed by identical I.R. spectra.

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